

BENEFITS OF THROMBOLYSIS BEFORE HOSPITALIZATION FOR ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT: The review describes the features of thrombolytic therapy in patients with acute myocardial infarction in detail. Thrombolytic therapy helps to reduce 30-day mortality in myocardial infarction from 17-18% to 5-8%. The issues of the optimal period of thrombolysis from the onset of the clinical manifestations of a heart attack, alternative methods for restoring coronary blood flow, indications and contraindications, complications and side effects, and methods for evaluating the effectiveness of thrombolysis are highlighted. The main fibrin-selective and fibrin-non-selective fibrinolytic drugs: streptokinase, alteplase, tenecteplase are listed. The results of large randomized clinical trials on fibrinolytic therapy of myocardial infarction are presented. The possibilities of increasing the effectiveness and safety of fibrinolytics by combining them with acetylsalicylic acid and heparins are discussed.

KEYWORD: myocardial infarction, thrombolysis, fibrinolytics

Acute myocardial infarction (AMI) in most cases develops as a result of intracoronary thrombosis formed over damaged atherosclerotic plaque [12]. Thrombolytic drugs began to be used in patients with acute myocardial infarction more than 50 years ago. Over the years, it has been shown that emergency restoration of coronary blood flow leads to a decrease in the focus of necrosis, makes the process of its formation reversible, and prevents the deterioration of the function of the affected myocardium. The use of thrombolytic therapy led to a decrease in 30-day mortality in patients with myocardial infarction to 5-8%, while in the "pre-fibrinolytic era" it reached 17-18%. But it is obvious that even now myocardial infarction remains one of the most prognostic formidable diseases, with the largest number of deaths observed in the first hours of the disease: 28% of patients die during the first hour of the disease, 38% within 4 hours and 46% in the first hours. 24 hours [6,7,9,10]. In this connection, one of the main tasks of treating a patient with myocardial infarction is the earliest possible, complete and sustainable restoration of coronary blood flow [12].

All available guidelines are based on the results of RCTs comparing primary PCV and TLT, as well as data from registries [1, 13]. Since most of the guidelines were

published several years ago, the most recent results have obviously not been taken into account. All experts agree that the time factor is key and reperfusion therapy should be started as early as possible. The American Heart Association (AHA) and the American College of Cardiology (ACC) favor pre-hospital thrombolysis over PCI, emphasizing that the timing of therapy is more important than the method of reperfusion. The ACC and ACC guidelines state that prehospital thrombolysis can be performed if there is confirmation of MI with ST segment elevation on the ECG, interpreted by the on-site physician or referred to a specialist. Further, it is advisable to complete a reperfusion checklist to ensure that the patient has no contraindications to such therapy and to identify high-risk patients who will benefit more from primary PCI. Pre-hospital thrombolysis should be performed within 30 minutes from the arrival of the ambulance to the patient. If a fibrinolytic agent cannot be administered prehospital and if the patient is transported to a hospital where PCI is not possible, the door-to-needle time (from arrival at the hospital to thrombolytic administration) should not exceed 30 minutes. However, if the hospital has facilities for percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI), the door-to-balloon time (from arrival at the hospital to balloon inflation at the catheter lab) should not exceed 90 minutes [4]. If a patient is admitted to a center that is not equipped to perform percutaneous coronary intervention and cannot be transferred to another hospital and is unable to undergo percutaneous coronary intervention within 90 minutes of the first medical contact, thrombolytic therapy should be started no later than 30 minutes from admission to the hospital if no contraindications (level of evidence B). The goal of organizing the patient care system is the interval of the total "ischemic time" at the stages of care, not exceeding 120 minutes. The goal for each treatment step is to:

- ☐ the time from the onset of symptoms to the call of an ambulance - 5 minutes;
- ☐ transfer of the call by the EMS dispatcher to the EMS team - 1 min;
- ☐ arrival of the ambulance crew at the place of call - 8 minutes,
- ☐ conducting an ECG and deciding on prehospital fibrinolytic therapy, if possible, and the time before TLT will be less than 30 minutes;
- ☐ if it is decided to take the patient to the hospital without the possibility of PCI, the "door-to-needle" time should be less than 30 minutes;
- ☐ if it is decided to deliver the patient to the hospital with the possibility of PCI, the time from calling the ambulance to the start of the balloon insertion should be less than 90 minutes (if the patient is delivered by his own transport
- ☐ the "door-balloon" time should not exceed 90 minutes).

The latest guideline of the European Society of Cardiology [13] recommends reperfusion by PCI if the intervention is performed by an experienced surgeon within 120 minutes from the first medical contact (call for the EMS) or within 90 minutes from the first medical contact if the patient applied within 2 hours from the onset of symptoms and has a significant myocardial area at risk and a low risk of bleeding. Primary PCI is reasonable in patients with contraindications to TLT, and this method of reperfusion is preferred in patients with cardiogenic shock. In other cases, TLT should be done as quickly as possible.

If TLT was unsuccessful, a rescue PCV with a reasonable time delay (up to 12 hours from the onset of symptoms) is recommended. If thrombolysis was successful (more than 70% ST-segment decrease after 60-90 min, reperfusion arrhythmias, disappearance of chest pain), coronary angiography and under leather intervention are recommended in the absence of contraindications in a time period of 3-24 hours in order to avoid bleeding risk and minimize the risk of coronary vessel reocclusion [13]. On the contrary, the use of "facilitated" under leather intervention (the use of fibrinolysis or IIb-IIIa glycoprotein receptor blockers before angioplasty is not recommended). The NICE Institute in the UK supports reperfusion through TLT, recommending the latest agents, reteplase and tenecteplase, for pre-hospital thrombolysis. Administration of thrombolytics by bolus facilitates their use, but none of them has been shown to be superior to alteplase in terms of long-term prognosis. In the GUSTO III study, which included 15,060 patients, reteplase compared with tenecteplase did not differ in effect on 30-day mortality (7.47% versus 7.24%) and the cumulative incidence of death and disabling stroke (7.89% in compared to 7.91%). In the ASSENT II study, which included more than 17,000 patients, tenecteplase had a comparable effect on 30-day mortality (6.18% vs. 6.15%) and the combined end point of death and non-fatal stroke (7.11% vs. 04%) and the incidence of hemorrhagic strokes (0.93% versus 0.94%). The time factor is also decisive here and therapy should be started within 12 hours of the onset of symptoms.

European Institute for Resuscitation states: thrombolysis is indicated in the absence of contraindications if PCV is not possible hold within 90 minutes, or if the duration of symptoms is less than 3 hours and the time before PCV is more than 60 minutes. Under leather intervention is indicated if it can be performed within 90 min, if thrombolysis is contraindicated, in patients with cardiogenic shock, severe heart failure, or in patients presenting later than 3 hours from the onset of symptoms [2].

Comparison of thrombolysis with percutaneous coronary interventions in patients according to randomized clinical trials. RCTs have shown that primary Subcutaneous Invasion is more effective than fibrinolysis in patients with T-segment Elevation MI when performed by an experienced team within 90 min from the first medical contact [7]. Kelyu et al. evaluated 23 studies comparing primary Subcutaneous Incision with TLT using streptokinase or a fibrin-specific agent. Regardless of the thrombolytic drug, primary under leather intervention was more effective [7]. However, as noted in a meta-analysis of 6 randomized trials, prehospital thrombolysis had an advantage over in-hospital thrombolysis in terms of hospital mortality and could be performed up to 45 min earlier, potentially saving more myocardial volume and improving outcomes. the use is associated with a significant 17% reduction in hospital mortality compared with treatment initiated in the hospital [9]. This is especially important for countries and regions where there is no possibility at all to carry out under the skin accommodation or there is no possibility of invasive interventions around the clock. Only one CART1M study directly compared prehospital thrombolysis with primary under leather intervention. Patients who received thrombolysis within 2 hours of onset of symptoms showed a strong trend towards a reduction in 30-day mortality compared to those who underwent primary dermal insertion. In the time interval over 2 hours from the onset of symptoms, the difference between the groups changed towards the advantage of the primary skin placement. [11].The results of the CART1M study are consistent with the data of RNAA&E-2. which showed that if treatment was started within 3 hours from the onset of symptoms, the incidence of deaths was identical, but if patients were randomized later than 3 hours from the onset of symptoms, the mortality in the thrombolysis group was significantly higher [14]. The investigators concluded that if patients with ST-segment elevation MI could be transported to a hospital with the possibility of being placed under a skin pouch for 20-30 min, they should be placed under a leather pouch. If Under the Skin Insertion cannot be performed within 60 minutes, thrombolytic therapy should be given up to 3 hours from the onset of symptoms. TLT should not be used if more than 3 hours have passed since the onset of the pain syndrome and then the patient must be referred to the hospital for Under the Skin Surgery. Interestingly, in a meta-analysis of PCAT studies, 30-day mortality was twice as high in the fibrinolysis group if the delay in treatment was increased from 1 hour to more than 6 hours [4]. The frequency of reinfarctions was also higher in this group in proportion to the time of delay in therapy; in the group under the skin insertion, this

dependence was not recorded. Thus, the time delay before reperfusion remains the central point in the choice of reperfusion strategy [4].

Conclusion

If we consider the issue as a whole, there are not so many unclear moments in the conduct of reperfusion therapy at present, there are clear time limits for the implementation of one or another type of therapy. Although primary PCA is the strategy of choice, this procedure is often not available in the required time window. In this case, thrombolysis should be considered as the first step of treatment, with the possibility of systemic or salvage PCI. In countries and regions where PCV is not available around the clock, thrombolysis remains the only option and should be performed as soon as possible, preferably in the prehospital setting. The most recent data from both registries and RCTs suggest that a pharmaco-invasive strategy is probably the preferred strategy in patients treated with TLT. In this regard, it is necessary to establish an organized network of clinical evaluation, treatment and transportation and adapt it to local conditions for optimal management of patients with T-segment MI with subsequent monitoring of clinical results.

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